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Reflection of sound waves from the underside of rough ice canopy in the Arctic Ocean

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Introduction

Deployed instruments in the Arctic Ocean cannot easily communicate to surface or between other instruments (rigs, gliders) without using acoustics. Propagation of sound in arctic waters is therefore of paramount importance for oceanographic investigations, and a lot of effort has been directed towards such issues. The present report is inspired by observations on acoustic communication performed under the project «UNDER-ICE» in 2013 and described in more detail by Hope [1]. The purpose here is to investigate the influence of the ice sheet on the acoustic propagation, using the ray-model BELLHOP as a simulation tool. The report consists of a brief description of the acoustic environment relevant for the experiment, computation of the reflection coefficient from a plane ice sheet, and 3 different approaches to model the rough underside of the ice canopy.

The acoustic environment

The water column in arctic waters are dominated by strong sound speed gradients in particular near the surface. Acoustically this is described as a surface propagation channel of typically 200 m depth, where sound is strongly interacting with the surface, whatever it consists of. Deeper down there is another sound channel where the sound is refracted upwards. This leads to convergence zones which in the UnderIce project were located about 35 km apart, depending on the sound source depth. Moreover, the sound speed profile is varying with horizontal range, but in the present case this is small enough to be ignored.

The bottom is not horizontal. The depth varies during the observations because the transmitter and receiver were drifting slowly during the experiment. Typically the depth was 1600 m or more. In the present simulations the bottom is substituted with water of same properties at the bottom of the water column, in order to avoid bottom reflections, which were of less interest in this context.

The reflection from ice depends on its acoustic properties and its roughness. The structure of the underside of the ice is very complicated, often with tunnels and deep keels, and it is unrealistic to try and model all details directly. Some acoustic models include a “roughness-parameter” which to some extent accounts for roughness by a simplistic scattering model. This is not available in BELLHOP. Instead it is possible to specify both a reflection coefficient table, and a table of the actual underside of the surface. Measurements of the latter are very scarce, and were not available for the UnderIce project area. The main part of this report addresses 3 different approaches to simulate the rough underside of the ice canopy.

Data for ice parameters are chosen among typical values given in the literature, and for simplicity consists of only one layer of ice, 2 m thick, with the following sound speeds: compressional sound speed=3600 m/s, shear wave speed=1800 m/s, density=900 kg/m³, attenuation coefficient compressional waves=0.216 dB/λ, and attenuation coefficient for shear waves=0.648 dB/λ.

Figure 1-1: Map of reflection coefficient magnitude – 2m plane ice sheet.

Simulations

The reflection coefficient is computed with the model described in [2]. A map of the reflection coefficient is presented in Figure 1-1. The reflection coefficient at 900 Hz is shown in Figure 1-2.

It is evident that for grazing incidence angles less than 20 degrees the reflection is almost total.

The environment file for BELLHOP used in this report is, with minor adjustments as follows:

```

1      'Case71 ssp,Inkoherent plane, vacuum' ! TITLE
2      900.0      !freq(Hz)
3      1          !Nmedia
4      'SVW'      !Opt1 V=vacuum, F=.trc-fil *=.ati-fil
5      0 0.0 2000.0 ! NMESH SIGMA DEPTH_of_BOTTOM (m)
6      0.0 1434.6/! sound speed profile
7      3.0 1434.6/
8      47.925 1435.9 / !1027.5
9      92.85 1438.2/ !1028
10     137.78 1444.7 !1028.4
11     182.7 1450.3/ !1028.7
12     227.63 1453.1/ !1029
13     407.33 1454.7/ !1029.9
14     452.25 1454.4/ !1030.1
15     676.88 1454.5 /!1031.2
16     811.65 1455.6 /!1031.9
17     991.35 1457.7/ !1032.8
18     1171.1 1460.0 /! 1033.6
19     1485.5 1464.6/ !1035.1
20     1800.0 1469.5 / !1036.6
21     2000.0 1469.5 /
22     'A' 0.0          ! Bottom parameters:
23     2000.0 1469.5 0.0 1.0 0.0 0.000 /! depth, compressional speed, shear speed, density, atten.
24     1          !NS=number of sound sources
25     60.0       !Sd(m) = depth of sound source
26     501        !1 !NRD= number of receiver depths
27     0.0 1000.0/ !90.0 / !RD= receiver depths (evenly distributed)
28     801 !1     !NRR = number of receiver ranges
29     0.0 40.0 /! RR (km) = receiver ranges (evenly distributed)
30     'I' 'C' ! 'E' !Output type: I=incoherent, C=coherent, E=eigenrays, A=arrivals
31     0          !5001 != number of rays (0=optimize)
32     -40.0 40.0 /!range of transmit angles
33     0.0 2001.0 280.0 !box size

```


Figure 1-2: Reflection coefficient at 900 Hz from 2 m plane ice sheet.

Figure 1-3: Sound speed profile.

Of special importance is line 4. Here “S” indicates spline interpolation of the sound speed profile (lines 6-21). “V” indicates vacuum above the surface. For a table of reflection coefficients it is replaced by “F”, and the code will look for a reflection coefficient file of the same name as the environmental file, but extension “.trc”. The “W” indicates the format for specifying attenuation. Finally, if the surface is not plane an “*” at the end indicates there is a file with extension “.ati” containing the actual surface coordinates. The “.ati-file” contains 355

tabulated incidence angles and coefficients. Bellhop ignores the phase shift of the coefficients.

The sound speed profile is illustrated in Figure 1-3. The red stars are the data input to Bellhop. In the plot linear interpolation is shown, not the spline actually used by BELLHOP.

In Figure 1-4 and 1-5 is shown the transmission loss (TL) map for a plane surface and a plane ice sheet of 2 m thickness, both with vacuum above. All simulations are with the sound source at 60 m. The effect of the surface duct is easily seen. Moreover, there is very little difference between the two cases! To illustrate this further Figure 1-6 shows TL at 90 m depth for the two cases. The difference is marginal! From this we may conclude that plane ice sheets have negligible effect on the TL of sound below 1 kHz trapped in the surface channel. This is to be expected from Figure 1-1, since the rays trapped in this channel hardly exceeds ± 10 degrees in grazing incidence, which is easily shown by simulations of ray arrivals with BELLHOP.

Figure 1-4: TL map with plane surface with vacuum above.

Figure 1-5: TL map with plane ice sheet 2 m thick, with vacuum above.

Figure 1-6: Comparison of TL at 90 m without and with 2m ice.

Rough ice interface

Below is presented 3 different methods for simulating the rough underside of the ice sheet. These are:

1. Inspired by P. Alexander et al. [3], who reported some statistics obtained from 2 drafts taken in the Arctic in August 1998.
2. Based on statistics presented by Wadhams et al. [4] from sonar transects in winter 2007 in the Fram strait.
3. Based on ice draft data made available by NSIDC (National Snow and Ice Data Center), [5].

Method 1.

Assume that the ice canopy may be simulated by a series of simple unit-structures (shown upside down):

The lengths r_1 - r_3 are randomly selected, as is also the height y_2 . This is done by using 6 random numbers $R(n)$. Three of these, $R(1)$, $R(2)$ and $R(4)$ are used to determine y_2 as follows:

$F=R(1)*(1+9*(R(2)>Thres))$, and $y_2=F*R(4)$. «Thres» is a fixed threshold chosen at liberty in the range $0<Thres<1$.

The Matlab code for this is:

```
function [x,y]=run
Thres=0.8; % for example
R=rand(1,6);
F=R(1)*(1+9*(R(2)>Thres));
y=zeros(1,3);
y(2)=F*R(4);
x(1)=R(3); %r1
x(2)=x(1)+R(5); %r2
x(3)=x(2)+R(6); %r3
```

In the first point one puts $x=y=0$. The maximum value of F is $10 R(1)$. The flexibility is reduced by putting $R(1)=1$, and it leads to a sharp kink in the distribution of keels. One may also introduce a minimum ice thickness by adding a fixed value to y .

To assemble this into an ice canopy we put a number of unity structures in series:

```

%script Islag.m
%4/4-2016 HH
[xx yy thres]=run;
x=[0 xx];%
y=[0 yy];% first point
for i=1:2000
[x,y]=run;
xx=[xx x+xx(end)];
yy=[yy y];
end
plot(xx,y)

```

An example is shown in Figure 2-1.

Figure 2-1: An example of ice-keels

Figure 2-2 shows an enlarged version of the same keels, to illustrate details near $y=0$.

It is of interest to study the distribution of ice-keels. Figure 2-3 shows the number of keels divided in 0.2 m intervals. With the current Thres value (0.8) the distribution has a strong kink near 1 m.

Figure 2-2: Enlarged version of keels.

Figure 2-3: Distribution of keel heights, Thres=0.8

Figure 2-4: Distribution of keels heights, Thres=0.2

necessary. We may later scale the range to wanted length and accordingly adjust the number of keels per km.

The change in the distribution of keels is easily seen. Which is to prefer is harder to determine.

As mentioned above, if $R(1)=1$ the kink is too sharp, regardless of the Thres value, as shown in Figure 5.

So far we have not discriminated between the keels. Alexander *et al.* assumes a threshold based on local minima about each keel, which is meaningless here since we have put the minimum value equal to zero.

In this example the number of unit-structures is arbitrarily chosen to 2000, and the distance unit is tacitly put to 1 m. This is not

We need to find a way to identify the real keels from the small ones which acts more like noise. Instead of using Alexander *et al.*'s definition we need another. As a first

suggestion: find the mean height, h , of all keels (except y -values = 0), and sample those that have amplitude $h*f$, where f is an adjustable factor. For example like this:


```
mm=find(yy>0);
h=mean(yy(mm)); % mean keel height
M=find(yy>h*f);
L=length(M); % number of keels larger than a threshold
plot(xx,yy) % plot ice canopy
hold on
plot(xx(M),yy(M),'*') % mark these with stars
Y=max(yy) %maximum keel-height
MRH=mean(yy(M)) % mean keel height above the threshold
```

Figure 2-5: Distribution of keel heights, $R(1)=1$.

An example is shown in Figure 2-6. It is also relevant to examine the distribution of keel heights – see Figure 2-7.

Figure 2-6: Keels above the minimum.

Figure 2-7: Keel distributions, 3 different runs with the same parameters.

(Note that in this example the ice range is half that of the previous example: therefore $N=7.6$ instead of 15.2).

Alexander applies measurements of ice drafts made by University of Colorado in August 1998. Here there are many keels with keel densities 10.2 and 16 keels per km, and mean keel heights of 3.4 and 3.7 m. By adjusting the parameters we may obtain the following characteristics over 40 km range:

I=2000, Thres=0.5, f=1:	L	Ymax	h	MRH	N
		615	9.62	1.35	3.66
		618	9.16	1.39	3.73
I=2000, Thres=0.5, f=1.5:	461	9.83	1.35	4.34	11.53
		460	9.29	1.36	4.42
I=1000, Thres=0.5, f=1.5:	237	9.65	1.42	4.48	5.95

where L =number of keels above the threshold, Y_{max} =maximum keel height, h =mean ice thickness, MRH = mean keel height above threshold and N =keels/km. The runs with $I=2000$, $Thres=0.5$ and $f=1$ match approximately the two parameters Alexander *et al.* supplies, which encourages application of these ice structures in Bellhop.

A few examples are shown below, using the same parameters as before, and ranges up to 40 km. All cases are simulated assuming incoherence. The transmission loss without ice

Figure 2-8: Transmission loss with rough surface, with vacuum above.

Figure 2-9: Transmission loss with rough surface and ice sheet.

(plane surface) and with a plane ice sheet 2 m thick is shown in Figure 1-4 and 1-5.

The roughness file with $I=2000$ contains 6006 ranges, and takes excessive time in Bellhop to compute. Instead $I=1000$ was used (last example above), with 3003 ranges. Figure 2-8 shows the case with vacuum above rough surface, while Figure 2-9 combines rough surface and ice sheet.

The rough surface itself is shown in Figure 2-10, and the corresponding pdf-distribution of ice drafts in Figure 2-11. This distribution does, however, not match observations made in the Arctic Ocean, and a more realistic model was sought.

Figure 2-10: Plot of the rough surface.

Figure 2-11: Size distribution of drafts.

Finally, Figure 2-12 shows a comparison of transmission-losses at 90 m depth computed for the 4 different cases: plane vacuum, plane ice, rough vacuum, rough ice. As before it is very apparent here that the damping due to the 2 m ice is completely negligible! It is also clear that the rough ice sheet has much stronger damping, and even with rough interface the ice sheet itself has negligible influence.

Figure 2-12: TL at 90 m depth, 4 different surfaces.

Method 2.

Diachock [4] suggested a Rayleigh distribution of keel-heights, but without justification. Wadhams *et al.* presents distributions from observations made in the Arctic Ocean in 2004 and 2007. The newest ones have 2 maxima in the distribution, and it is tempting to try and approximate such a distribution. The profile chosen here is from the Fram Strait, 81.7 – 83.8 °N, 4-8 °W, 2007, and is shown in Figure 3-1, with it's approximation in Figure 3-2. The method starts by generating a set of ice thicknesses having the same pdf-profile distributed across a given range. This is done in the Matlab code «Wadhams2.m» given in the Appendix. The observed profile is approximated by 3 Gaussian distributions which are summed to give $y(x)$, where x is ice thickness. Next, one randomly draws values according to the following procedure: First make a cumulative sum of y , $S = \text{cumsum}(y)$, followed by $z = 1 - S/S(\text{end})$, where $S(\text{end})$ is the final value of S . z is accordingly normalized with its largest value $z(x=0) = 1$. Now one may start sampling $x(z)$ randomly. Here we use $a = \text{rand}$, which returns a value between 0 and 1. The closest value of z is selected: $k = \text{find}(z < a)$. k is a vector but we need only the first member: $h = x(k(1))$. This is repeated until the desired number of samples are obtained. In Figure 2-3 the result of sampling 3000 heights are shown. The

Figure 3-1: Draft profile from Wadhams *et al.* [2].

Figure 3-2: Wadhams profile and approximated distribution.

correspondence with the observations is satisfactory. The 3000 heights must now be distributed across a range of for example 40 km. If this is done uniformly we get a surface profile as shown in Figure 3-4.

Figure 3-3: Draft distribution in simulation with Bellhop.

Figure 3-4: Rough surface profile, Case10A.

This surface may have correct parameters regarding mean ice thickness and keels/km, but not regarding horizontal correlation. The latter is approximately zero. In order to adjust the horizontal correlation we need to regroup the ice keels. As a first attempt the whole range was divided in a number of equal intervals (300), and the keels were sorted in each interval such that the largest keels were placed in the middle of the interval. This resulted in a too rigid distribution: The correlation length became equal to the interval length, which is very unrealistic. The next attempt uses un-equal interval lengths sampled from a normal distribution. Here we apply the same method as above: Let $\rho(x) = \exp(-x/L) \cdot \sqrt{2/\pi}$, where L is a measure of the correlation length, $SS = \text{cumsum}(\rho)$, $zz = 1 - SS/SS(\text{end})$, and sample random lengths (l) from zz . The largest interval length is $l=1$, which corresponds to $40 \times 10^3 / 300 \text{ m} = 133.33 \text{ m}$ if the total range is 40 km. With $L=0.3$ the real correlation length becomes $L * 40 \times 10^3 / 300 = 40 \text{ m}$. Figure 3-5 shows an example of distribution of intervals with $L=0.5$.

Figure 3-5: Interval length distribution, $L=0.5$.

Figure 3-6: Rough surface with sorted keels.

Now this shall be applied to the keels. As described above the keels are sorted within each half-interval such that the largest are gathered in the middle and else dropping off to each side. Figure 3-6 shows an example, with an enlarged version without and with sorting, to show the details in Figure 3-7. The process resembles a kind of low pass filtering of the keels. The statistics in terms of mean ice thickness and number of keels per km is unchanged, although dependent on how to define an ice keel. Alexander et al. [1] defines an ice keel to be larger than 2.5/2 of it nearest minima (which is not easy to apply for all cases). Figure 3-7 shows that the total number of keels (small and large) is considerably reduced after sorting. Strictly, according to this method of sorting the keels the number of large keels becomes equal to the number of intervals: $N=300/40=7.7$ per km, except that we here have not introduced any threshold.

Figure 3-7: Unsorted and sorted keels.

The code is written in terms of 4 scripts: Wadhams2, Hcorr, T1 og T2. T2 runs all the scripts and produces 4 figures and some statistics. The codes are discussed in Report_keels_distributed.odt. The translation of the keel data to Bellhops surface file is made with «to_ati.m» for the unsorted keels and «to_ati2.m» for the sorted ones.

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Figure 3-8: TL-plot of unsorted keels.

Figure 3-9: TL-plot of sorted keels.

Figure 3-10: TL and ray plot with unsorted keels.

Figure 3-11: TL-plots at depths 20, 100 and 200m.

Some simulations with these surfaces are done as Case11. Figure 3-8 shows unsorted keels and Figure 3-9 the sorted ones (unfortunately the titles on the figures are wrong!). The difference between the figures is not large. The dark blue part in the range 10-30 km is due to lack of rays in this region – it is effectively a shadow zone since the signal in the surface channel has vanished. This is also seen when the rays are plotted, Figure 3-10. This shadow zone is not present when the surface is plane, either with ice or vacuum. Moreover, it is evident that the convergence zone at about 35 km is not due to reflections from the bottom, but to refraction due to the sound speed profile.

A plot of the TL at fixed depths shows the shadow zone clearly, as a large dip in the level, Figure 3-11. It is a bit strange to see that TL is less after the dip than just before. This is obviously due to the convergence zone. We do not see this dip when the surface is even. This must mean that the degree of roughness must play a great importance. On the other hand it does not seem as if the correlation length is important, since whether the keels are sorted or not makes little difference. What matters are the keel height and their number.

In the examples used here the following parameters were used:

I=3000= total number of ice thicknesses in the range
R=40 km, range
L=0.5, relative correlation length
J=400, number of intervals on which to distribute the keels
Correlation length=50 m
Np=10, number of keels per km
Mean ice thickness=4.09 m
Median ice thickness=18.2 m
N_polly(usorted)= 9.325 keels per km

A more detailed comparison between sorted and unsorted keels is shown in Figure 3-12. As previously the presence of the ice sheet makes no visible difference, and it is hard to discriminate the effects of sorting the keels.

The figures below were computed with unsorted keels. Figure 3-15 compares the transmission-losses. The ice sheet damps almost as much at the rough surface. This is in contrast to the case Method 1, where the rough surface damped less than the ice. In other words, the roughness of Method 2 damps stronger than Method 1.

Figure 3-12: Comparison of TL at 90 m depth.

Figure 3-13: Transmission loss, rough surface M2, vacuum.

Figure 3-14: Transmission loss, rough M2 surface with ice.

Figure 3-16: TL at 90 m depth, different surfaces.

Method 3

The last method applies upward looking sonar ice draft data, made available by National Snow & Ice Data Center [5]. The dataset used here is identified as 2005e r19-00, recorded Nov 2 2005, at a segment located at Beginning Latitude: 84.4, Beginning Longitude: 26.2, Ending Latitude: 84.1, Ending Longitude: 25.2 (degrees). The number of drafts are 25693,

Figure 4-1: Ice profile - r19-00, original.

Figure 4-2: Draft distribution – original.

over a range 35.641 km. Figure 4-1 shows the ice profile, and Figure 4-2 the draft distribution, extended to 40 km. To achieve this the draft profile was prolonged with a flipped version of itself, and then truncated. However, with the original ice profile Bellhop failed to provide reasonable results, even after 6 hours cpu time.

It turns out that Bellhop acts strangely to such input – a ray plot shows that after about 25 km every ray vanish or are reflected in the backwards direction. Actually, the ray plot proceeds to more than -250 km, as exemplified in Figure 4-3. This behavior has not been explained. To resolve this problem the profile was reduced in several steps. First it was halved by taking the mean value of

Figure 4-3: Ray plot with original surface, r19-00.

Figure 4-4: Draft distribution - reduced by 8

successive pairs, resulting in 14401 drafts. This was still too much. A repetition gave 7200 drafts, still too much. Finally, another halving to 3600 drafts gave reasonable results. Thus, the number of drafts were reduced by 8. Figure 4-4 shows that the draft distribution is essentially the same as originally. For simplicity the latter are referred to as Wens8 and Wens4, respectively. TL simulations at 90 m shows that Wens8 and Wens4 give the same loss as long as Wens4 behaves reasonable.

Figure 4-5 shows an expanded plot of the original Wens profile together with Wens8. The dominating features are kept in the Wens8 profile.

Figure 4-5: Comparison of original draft profile and Wens8.

Figure 4-6: TL at 90 m depth with Wens4 and Wens8 profiles.

Figure 4-7: TL map with Wens8 surface, no ice, fluid bottom.

Figure 4-8: TL map with Wens 8 surface, 2m ice sheet, fluid bottom.

Figure 4-9: TL at 90 m depth with different surfaces, fluid bottom.

Figures 4-7 – 4-9 illustrates the effects of different surfaces. When the surface is plane and totally reflecting the surface channel traps most of the sound, see Figure 1-4. If the surface is still totally reflecting but rough (with Wens8 r19-00 profile) much of the sound is scattered away from the surface channel, and whatever sound is interacting with the surface becomes widely scattered – Figure 4-7. If also an ice sheet is included the damping is marginally increased – Figure 4-8. In Figure 4-9 the transmission loss at 90 m depth is plotted for the cases: A) plane surface (vacuum), B) plane 2 m thick ice sheet, C) rough surface (vacuum) and D) rough surface with ice sheet. The jump seen at 33 km in Cases B-D is due to the convergence zone of the refracted waves. The plane ice sheet is not causing a significant increase in TL. Together (Case D) the TL at 33 km has increased by 61 dB (before the refracted waves appears).

In the simulations shown Wens8 roughness was used. Some statistics of Wens8:

- mean ice thickness=2.68 m
- std = 1.81 m
- maximum ice draft = 13.89 m
- Number of keels:
- f=1.5 : N1.5=89/km
- f=3 : N3 = 85.8 /km
- f=4 : N4 = 83.6 /km
- f=5 : N5 = 40.36 /km

The density of keels far exceeds those found by Alexander *et al.*, although the definitions of keels are somewhat unequal.

The correlation length may be found by the “height-height” correlation function introduced by Bloomfield [7]. Figure 4-10 shows an example using Wens8. The correlation length, L , is found when the correlation function bends over and approaches a constant

level, as indicated by the red circle in Figure 4-10. It is here located at 14 lags, corresponding to $L=134$ m. Applied to the other rough surfaces one finds:

Wens-original: (Method 3)	$L=77$ m
Wens2:	$L=74$ m
Wens4:	$L=131$ m
Wens8:	$L=134$ m
Case68: (Method 1)	$L=16$ m
unsorted:(Method 2)	$L=13$ m
sorted: (Method 2)	$L=67$ m.

Why L changes when the roughness scale is changed has not been investigated. It seems anyway that the influence of the correlation length is marginal.

Figure 4-10: Bloomfield's Height-Height correlation function

Discussion and conclusion

Both the reflection coefficient of the ice sheet and the roughness of the ice underside is important sources of transmission loss. 3 different approaches to generate a rough underside were applied. As evident from Figure 4-11, which compares the TL due to the rough surfaces with vacuum on top, Method 1 and Method 3 results in almost the same transmission loss, while Method 2 provides a much larger loss. From Figures 1-14, 2-16 and 4-9 it also appears

Figure 4-11: Comparison of TL with the 3 methods.

that the damping due to the reflection coefficient of the ice sheet is insignificant compared to the roughness. This is not surprising, considering that the reflection coefficient is very close to 1 for grazing incidences less than 10 degrees, which is the case for waves trapped in the surface channel.

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Appendices – matlab codes

1. Method 1

Main program: «Islag.m», applies «run.m». «run» generates one unit-structure.

```
%skript Islag.m
%4/4-2016 HH
clear
f=1.5;
[xx yy Thres]=run;
x=[0 xx];%
y=[0 yy];%
I=2000;
for i=1:I
[x,y]=run;
xx=[xx x+xx(end)];
yy=[yy y];
end
figure(1)
plot(xx,yy)
mm=find(yy>0);
h=mean(yy(mm));
hold on
M=find(yy>h*f);
L=length(M) % number of keels above threshold
plot(xx(M),yy(M),'*')
xlabel('Range - arbitrary units')
ylabel('Keel height - m')
title(['I = ' num2str(I) ', thres = ' num2str(Thres) ', f = ' num2str(f) ', mean height = ' num2str(h) ', N = '
num2str(L/40)])
Y=max(yy)%maximum height of keels
MRH=mean(yy(M))%mean height of keels
hold off
figure(2)
t=[0.2:0.2:9];
for i=1:length(t)
nn=find(yy>t(i));
N(i)=length(nn);
```

```

end
plot(t,N)
---
% run
function [x,y,thres]=run
thres=0.5;
R=rand(1,6);
F=R(1)*(1+9*(R(2)>thres));
y=zeros(1,3);
y(2)=F*R(4);
x(1)=R(3);
x(2)=x(1)+R(5);
x(3)=x(2)+R(6);
---

```

2. Method 2.

Main code: T2 calls the needed subroutines. Transfer to *.ati file by to_ati.m or to_ati2.m.

```

%T2: skript for å kombinere Wadhams og kjøldanner
% 23/5-2016 HH
Wadhams2
Hcorr
T1
figure(3)
plot(Range,HH)
xlabel('Range - km')
ylabel('Ice thickness - m')
title('Sorted ice keels - Gaussian distribution')
figure(4)
hist(l,30,L*23.5)
hold on
plot(xx,Rho,'r')
xlabel('Normalized length distribution')
legend('Final','Assumed')
title(['Distribution of keel "wavelengths", correlation length: ' num2str(L)])
hold off
%CorrLength=L/sum(l)*R*1000
CorrLength=L*R*1e3/J
% beregner litt statistikk på HH
for i=1:4
NN(i)=length(find(HH>i*5));
end
DH=[5 10 15 20]
Keels_per_km=NN/R
Mean_HH=mean(HH)
Mode_HH=mode(HH)
Median_HH=median(HH)
N=0;
H=zeros(size(HH));
for i=1:I-11
if(HH(i+1)>HH(i))
H(i)=HH(i);
end
end
end
---

%skript Wadhams2.m 11/5-16 HH
%beregner iskjøler basert på Wadhams statistikk for Framstredet,
I=3000; %antall i Range
R=40;%km, største lengde
Range=[1:I]/I*R;
x1=1.8;%1.85; % første topp

```

```

s1=0.45;%0.40;
A1=0.25; %amplituden
x2=3.5;%4.0; %andre topp
s2=2.1;%3.0;
A2=0.55;
x3=7; %tredje topp
s3=4;
A3=0.25;%0.3;
x=[0:0.01:18];%[0:0.01:22]; % høyder
y1=normpdf(x,x1,s1);
y2=normpdf(x,x2,s2);
y3=normpdf(x,x3,s3);
y=A1*y1+A2*y2+A3*y3;
x4=[0.41237 0.61856 1.03093 1.23711 1.36082 1.44330 1.75258 2.06186 2.26804 2.88660 3.09278
4.74227 5.77320 7.21649 8.65979 10.00000 17.31959]; % målepunkter Wadhams
y4=[0.037578 0.05 0.1 0.15 0.2 0.25 0.3 0.25 0.2 0.15 0.12996 0.10 0.075157 0.05 0.025052 0.014092 0];
figure(1)
S=cumsum(y);
z=1-S/S(end);
%danner samling av høyder slik:
for i=1:I
a=rand;
k=find(z<a);
h(i)=x(k(1));
end
figure(1)
plot(Range,h) % plotter isflaten!
xlabel('Range - km')
ylabel('Ice draft')
title('Rough ice surface')
%sjekker fordelingen
figure(2)
hist(h,88,5)
hold on
plot(x,y,'r',x4,y4,*)
xlabel('Ice draft')
ylabel('pdf')
title("'pdf" for model Wadhams, Fram Strait')
legend('Final','Ideal','Wadhams2')
hold off
% beregner litt statistikk
for i=1:4
NN(i)=length(find(h>i*5));
end
DH=[5 10 15 20]
Keels_per_km=NN/R
Mean=mean(h)
Mode=mode(h)
Median=median(h)
N=0;
H=zeros(size(h));
for i=1:I-11
if(h(i+1)>h(i))
H(i)=h(i);
end
end
[k1,k2]=find(H>0);
for i=2:length(k2)
if(H(k2(i))>2.5/2*h(k2(i)-1))
N=N+1;
end
end
end

```

```

N_polly=N/R
----

%Hcorr - 23/5-2016 HH – horizontal correlation length
%Lager Gaussfordelt horisontal bølgelengde
L=0.5; % Korr-lengde -
J=400; % antall lengder
xx=[0:0.01:1];
Rho=exp(-(xx/L).^2);%/sqrt(2*pi); % fordelingen
SS=cumsum(Rho);
zz=1-SS/SS(end);
for i=1:J
    a=rand;
    k=find(zz<a);
    l(i)=xx(k(1));
endfor
LL=cumsum(l)/sum(l)*I;
---

%T1.m - sortering foregår her
% 23/5-2016 - HH
%J=300;
HH=zeros(1,length(h));
s1=1;
for i=1:J
s2=round((LL(i)));
s3=s1+round((s2-s1)/2);
hh=sort(h(s1:s3));
HH(s1:s3)=hh;
hh=fliplr(sort(h(s3+1:s2)));
HH(s3+1:s2)=hh;
s1=s2+1;
end
---

% to_ati.m script for lagring av .ati-data, 26/4-2016, HH, unsorted keels
%Antar at avstandsdata ligger i Range, høyde i h
DD=length(Range);
fid=fopen('unsorted.ati','w');
fprintf(fid,'L\n')
fprintf(fid,'%i\n',DD)
for i=1:DD
fprintf(fid,'%f %f\r\n',Range(i), h(i))
end
fclose(fid);
----

% to_ati2.m script for lagring av .ati-data, 26/4-2016, HH, sorted keels
%Antar at avstandsdata ligger i Range, høyde i HH
DD=length(Range);
fid=fopen('sorted.ati','w');
fprintf(fid,'L\n')
fprintf(fid,'%i\n',DD)
for i=1:DD
fprintf(fid,'%f %f\r\n',Range(i), HH(i))
end
fclose(fid);
---
```

3. Method 3

The data is read from <ftp://sidads.colorado.edu/pub/DATASETS/NOAA/G01360/> and saved in local files. The data is then read by les_Wens.m and les_Wens_stat.m, where the latter reads some statistics. The main code is To_Wens.m which also decimates the data set.

```
%To_Wens.m, skript for å lage ati-filer av Wensdata
%Vær i Wadhamsdata, addpath HTEST

file='2005e/2005e r19 - 00_ - release.Ser';
les_Wens
YY=[Y flipr(Y)];% forleng Y
RR=[R R+R(end)];
[n1,n2]=find(RR>40000);
YH=(YY(1:n2(1)));
RH=(RR(1:n2(1)));%så langt som før
RH2=(RH(1:2:end-1)+RH(2:2:end))/2;% halvering
YH2=(YH(1:2:end-1)+YH(2:2:end))/2;
RH4=(RH2(1:2:end-1)+RH2(2:2:end))/2;% halvering
YH4=(YH2(1:2:end-1)+YH2(2:2:end))/2;
RH8=(RH4(1:2:end-1)+RH4(2:2:end))/2;% halvering
YH8=(YH4(1:2:end-1)+YH4(2:2:end))/2;
Range=RH8/1000;
h=YH8;
to_ati
Range=RH4/1000;
HH=YH4;
to_ati2;%the sorted.ati and unsorted.ati should be renamed % manually
---
```

```
%les_Wens.m skript for å lese draft-data fra Wadhams
fid=fopen(file,'r');
for i=1:32
TT=fgetl(fid);
end
N=str2num(TT(24:end));% antall avlesninger
for i=33:40
TT=fgetl(fid);
end
for i=1:N
ray(:,i)=fscanf(fid,'%f, %f',2);
end
R=ray(1,:);
Y=ray(2,:); %draft
fclose(fid);
figure
plot(R,Y)
xlabel('Range - m')
ylabel('Ice draft - m')
title(file)
---
```

```
%les_Wens_stat.m skript for å lese statistikk-data fra %Wadhams
fid=fopen(file,'r')
for i=1:49
TT=fgetl(fid);
end
for i=1:350
Ray(:,i)=fscanf(fid,'%f, %f, %f',3);
end
figure
```

```

plot(Ray(2,:),Ray(3,:))
fclose(fid)
xlabel('Draft - m')
ylabel('pdf')
title(file)
axis( [ 0 15 0 .08 ] )
---
```

4. Other codes

```

function [A,L,k]=autokorr(y,maxlag)
% Includes Bloomfield height-height correlation function (H)
%autokorr.m
n=length(y);
Y=y-mean(y);
YY=[Y Y];
for i=1:n
a(i)=Y*YY(i:i+n-1)';
end
[n1,n2]=max(a);
A=a(n2:n2+maxlag-1)/std(y)^2;
L=1:maxlag;
A=A/max(A);
[k1 k2]=find(A>1/e);
k(1)=k2(end);
[k1 k2]=find(A>1/sqrt(2));
k(2)=k2(end);
[k1 k2]=find(A>1/2);
k(3)=k2(end);
for i=1:maxlag
H(i)=sum((Y(1:maxlag)-Y(i:i+maxlag-1)).^2)/maxlag;
end
plot(H)
title('Bloomfield correlation length method')
xlabel('Lag')
[n1,n2]=find(diff(H)<0);%finn knekkpunkt
k(4)=n2(1);
hold on
plot(k(4),H(k(4)),'ro')
hold off
```